

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THICK COMPOSITE PLATE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A simple approach for the accurate evaluation of transverse (interlaminar) stresses in thick composite plates is to use a two-dimensional shear deformation theory to calculate the in-plane stresses, and then apply the three-dimensional equilibrium equations to determine the interlaminar stresses. This approach can predict interlaminar stresses accurately, without resorting to very cumbersome three-dimensional modeling or second order shear theory.

A study was conducted utilizing a two-dimensional finite element (based on Mindlin type first order shear theory) to model the laminated plate structures for calculating force resultants and corresponding in-plane ply stresses in the laminate. Plate comparisons show that for length to thickness (L/T) ratios of 10 or more, first order shear theory provides sufficiently accurate deflection and strain results for composite glass plates. A post-processor was written to integrate equations of equilibrium to compute interlaminar stresses, utilizing in-plane stress values for each ply. Interlaminar stress results computed by integrating equations of equilibrium show good comparison with the results from layered finite element modeling. The proposed method, therefore, is a practical alternative for obtaining in-plane as well as interlaminar components of stress in large complex laminated structures.

KEYWORDS: Thick Composites; Plates; Interlaminar; Stress; Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

With increasing interest in the use of composite materials in high technology areas, it is important that their failure/fracture mode be predicted reliably. Failure phenomenon in composite materials is extremely complex. Nevertheless, the delamination mode of failure is now recognized as the most critical (1). Initiation and/or growth of this failure mode is due to interlaminar stresses σ_{xz} , σ_{yz} , and σ_z shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Three Dimensional State of Stress in a Composite Laminate

Analytical solutions to determine interlaminar stresses are few and are usually restricted to problems with simple loading and boundary conditions. The Finite Element Method (FEM) is, therefore, a practical alternative for the solution of such complex structures. The present study focuses on two-dimensional elements (based on Mindlin type first order shear theory) to account for transverse shear deformation, as the use of three-dimensional models or higher order shear theory for complicated geometry is computationally expensive and, therefore, not feasible for practical composite structures.

The procedure is completely integrated as pre- and post-processors to the general purpose finite element programs such as ANSYS (2) or NASTRAN. Smearred properties of the laminate are first determined using pre-processor programs such as GENLAM (3). The finite element program is then used to determine laminate strains and curvature (using Mindlin type first order shear theory elements).

From the laminate strains for each element, in-plane ply stresses are determined using the FORTRAN version of the program GENLAM. A post-processor is written to integrate equations of equilibrium to compute interlaminar stresses, utilizing in-plane ply stresses.

Three-dimensional stress components for each ply are required in the in-ply and inter-ply failure criteria suggested by S.W.Tsai. A pre-processor to the SUPERTAB (4) computer program was written for the graphical display of the strength ratio for each element of the finite element model obtained using the in-ply failure criteria. This plot is similar to the von-Mises stress plot for isotropic materials. Interfaces between various programs are written such that no manual data transfer is required.

2. THICK COMPOSITE LAMINATE MODELING

It is important to consider transverse shear deformation in the modeling of thick composite plate structures. Plate parameters that affect transverse shear deformation are the L/T ratio of the plate, its support conditions and the ratio of transverse shear modulus to the in-plane modulus of the plate material. Most of the composite materials in use to date have a low ratio of the transverse shear modulus to the in-plane modulus. Therefore, transverse shear deformation plays a much more important role in composite plates than in corresponding metallic plates.

A study was performed to determine whether modeling by Mindlin type first order shear theory provides a reasonably accurate response of the composite glass plate for L/T ratios of 10 or more. The L/T ratio for laminates in armored composite vehicle hulls generally falls within this range. The composite plate material selected for this study was S2-Glass/Polyester woven material. Modeling of the plate for comparison purposes was done using the ANSYS first order shear theory element (STIF43), three-dimensional solid element (STIF45), and the classical plate bending element for thin plates (STIF63) where shear deformation is ignored. Only one quarter of the plate was modeled due to symmetry. Three solid elements through the thickness were modeled with the STIF45 element. Figure 2 shows the simply supported square orthotropic plate. Smearred orthotropic material properties of the laminate are listed in Table 1. Two load cases were evaluated: a point load at the center of the plate and a uniformly distributed load applied over the entire plate. Results in Table 2 show that for glass reinforced composite plates with L/T ratios of 10 or more, first order shear theory based on two-dimensional elements provide sufficiently accurate results. Results from classical plate bending theory, where shear deformation is ignored, exhibit a large percentage of error. Thus, Mindlin type first order shear theory elements from the ANSYS general purpose finite element program accurately predict the global response of armored composite vehicle hull structures.

Table 1 - Orthotropic Material Properties of a Woven S-2 Glass/Polyester Quasi-Isotropic Laminate

PROPERTY	LAMINATE VALUE
E1 = E2	15.72 GPa
E3	4.89 GPa
G12	6.83 GPa
V12	0.243
V13 = V23	0.28
G13 = G23	2.07 GPa

Table 2 - Response Comparison of Simply Supported Square Composite Plate Using Different Analysis Approaches

PLATE LENGTH TO THICKNESS RATIO (L/T)	APPLIED LOAD	PLATE CENTER DEFLECTION (cm)				
		3-D SOLID ELEMENT STIF45	MINDLIN FIRST ORDER SHEAR THEORY STIF43	% ERROR	CLASSICAL PLATE BENDING ELEMENT STIF63	% ERROR
30	UNIFORMLY APPLIED LOAD	.09517	.09540	0.24	.08915	6.56
	POINT LOAD IN THE CENTER	.28042	.28146	0.37	.25580	8.77
20	UNIFORMLY APPLIED LOAD	.02967	.02964	0.08	.02642	10.96
	POINT LOAD IN THE CENTER	.09322	.09108	2.28	.07579	18.7
10	UNIFORMLY APPLIED LOAD	.00450	.00437	2.82	.00330	26.5
	POINT LOAD IN THE CENTER	.01575	.01598	1.45	.00947	39.8

LENGTH, L (cm)	THICKNESS, T (cm)	L/T RATIO
38.1 (15 in)	1.27 (0.5 in)	30
38.1 (15 in)	1.91 (0.75 in)	20
38.1 (15 in)	3.81 (1.5 in)	10

Figure 2 - Simply Supported Square Orthotropic Plate with Finite Element Size 1.27 cm x 1.27 cm (0.5 in x 0.5 in)

3. INTERLAMINAR STRESS COMPUTATION

The interlaminar shear stresses were computed by integrating the equilibrium equations of elasticity for each layer of the laminate. In incremental form, interlaminar stresses $\Delta \sigma_{xz}$ and $\Delta \sigma_{yz}$ from equilibrium equations can be written as:

$$\Delta \sigma_{xz} = -\Delta z \left(\frac{\Delta \sigma_x}{\Delta x} + \frac{\Delta \sigma_{xy}}{\Delta y} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta \sigma_{yz} = -\Delta z \left(\frac{\Delta \sigma_{yx}}{\Delta x} + \frac{\Delta \sigma_y}{\Delta y} \right) \quad (2)$$

The right hand side in equations (1) and (2) are the increments of in-plane ply stresses. The 8-noded finite element with its four integration points used in calculating the in-plane stress increments is shown in Figure 3. Thus, increment $\Delta \sigma_x$ for layer j was calculated as:

$$\Delta \sigma_x^j = (\sigma_x^3 + \sigma_x^4 - \sigma_x^1 - \sigma_x^2)^j / 2.0$$

where $(\sigma_x^3)^j$ = stress in element x direction in layer j at integration point 3
 and $\Delta x, \Delta y$ are as shown in Figure 3.

The interlaminar shear stresses between layer k and layer k+1 are then computed as:

$$\sigma_{xz}^k = \sum_{j=1}^k \Delta \sigma_{xz}^j - A_x \sum_{j=1}^k t_j \tag{3}$$

$$\sigma_{yz}^k = \sum_{j=1}^k \Delta \sigma_{yz}^j - A_y \sum_{j=1}^k t_j \tag{4}$$

where A_x and A_y are the correction terms defined as:

$$A_x = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{NL} \Delta \sigma_{xz}^j}{t}$$

t = total thickness of laminate

and NL = total number of layers

The above definition with its correction terms satisfies the condition that interlaminar shear stresses be zero on the plate surfaces.

Figure 3 - 8-Noded Finite Element with its Four Integration Point Locations

Strains and curvature from the finite element model using the ANSYS 8-noded element STIF93 shown in Figure 3 are saved at the four integration points of the element. In-plane stresses σ_x^k , σ_y^k , and σ_{xy}^k for each ply at the four integration points are calculated using the FORTRAN version of the GENLAM computer program. A post-processor is written to calculate interlaminar stresses σ_{xz}^k and σ_{yz}^k from the in-plane stresses σ_x^k , σ_y^k , and σ_{xy}^k . In-plane strain curvature output from the finite element program is linked directly to the post-processor to avoid any manual transfer of data.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

In order to test the accuracy of the above formulation, a simply supported, symmetric, laminated, square plate with 8 layers [45/-45/45/-45]s of S-2 Glass/polyester material was analyzed under uniform pressure. Only one quarter of the plate, as shown in Figure 2, was modeled. Total span L of the plate was assumed to be 25.4 cm (10 inches) with a thickness T as 2.54 cm (1 inch). S-2 glass polyester ply properties and the equivalent orthotropic laminate properties are listed in Table 3. The finite element analysis was performed using the ANSYS STIF93 element. Strain and curvature from the finite element analysis were saved at four integration points within each element. The in-plane ply stresses at the four integration points and the interlaminar stresses between each ply in an element were then calculated using the post-processor program written for that purpose. Interlaminar stress results were also obtained using the ANSYS STIF91 layered shell element for comparison purposes. Normalized interlaminar shear stress results from both methods are identical as shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Table 3 - Ply and Laminate Properties of Woven S-2 Glass/Polyester [45/-45/45/-45]s Laminate

PROPERTY	PLY VALUE	ORTHOTROPIC LAMINATE VALUE [45/-45/45/-45]s
E1 = E2	20.68 GPa	12.13 GPa
E3	4.89 GPa	4.89 GPa
G12	4.14 GPa	9.58 GPa
V12	0.0823	0.46
V13 = V23	0.28	0.28
G13 = G23	2.07 GPa	2.07 GPa
DENSITY ρ	0.0133 Mg/m ³	0.0133 Mg/m ³

Figure 4 - Normalized Interlaminar Shear Stresses σ_{xz} and σ_{yz} Distribution Through the Plate Thickness at the Center of Plate ($q_0 = \text{Applied Load} = 6.8947 \times 10^{-3} \text{ MPa (1.0 psi)}$ and $L/T = 10$)

Figure 5 - Normalized Interlaminar Shear Stresses σ_{xz} and σ_{yz} Distribution Through the Plate Thickness at the Boundary ($q_0 = \text{Applied Load} = 6.8947 \times 10^{-3} \text{ MPa (1.0 psi)}$ and $L/T = 10$)

5. CONCLUSIONS

A simple approach for the accurate evaluation of interlaminar shear stress variations through the thickness of a thick laminated plate is presented. From the study conducted on thick composite glass plates, it has been shown that for a plate length to thickness ratio of 10 or more, first order shear theory provides sufficiently accurate results. Results obtained using thin plate theory which neglects transverse shear terms appear to be inadequate.

The use of two-dimensional elements (based on Mindlin type first order shear theory) to account for transverse shear deformation is a practical alternative, as the use of three-dimensional models or higher order shear theory for complicated geometry is computationally expensive. Calculation of interlaminar stresses by integrating three-dimensional equilibrium equations of elasticity was initially proposed by Pryor et al. (5) and has been used by other authors since then. The method results in a continuous distribution of shear stresses through the plate thickness. Interlaminar shear stress results obtained using this method were identical to the results obtained using a detailed ply-by-ply layered shell element model. Display of the strength ratio in graphical form similar to von-Mises stress plots for an isotropic material is quite helpful in identifying areas where lower or higher margins of safety exist.

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7. REFERENCES

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8. BIOGRAPHY

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